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A Study on Financial Literacy among the Rural Women in Tirunelveli District

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Abstract

Rural women in India are less educative compared to rural men. The theme of this study is to signify the financial literacy of women in rural areas in Tirunelveli district. Rural women are mostly uneducated and are mostly engaged in farming, agricultural, livestock rearing etc. This article has in depth analysed the knowledge to be required by the rural women to make proper financial planning for a long period in their life time. To know the financial literacy of rural women, a questionnaire has been framed and has been circulated among them. The feedback reveals that still financial literacy level among the rural women is not satisfactory and is to be guided properly. Due to lack of financial inclusion among rural women there are chances of financial malpractices and fraudulent activities occurring very frequently by the financial lenders and third parties. Various financial products and services should be informed and made known to the rural women. This paper aims to analyze the awareness and financial literacy level among rural women.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, Rural Women, Economic.

Introduction:

Nowadays, the need for financial literacy has become very vital due to rapid growth in financial markets and technological advancement in financial products. Financial literacy is to know about handling money, savings and investments to make judicious decision about their own financial resources. Because of the lack of financial knowledge one, fails to invest carefully and is indebted. Most of the women in rural areas suffer from economic poverty as well as from 'information poverty'. Rural women are considered to be the productive women in India's national economy. Rural women work for longer hours compared to men and substantially contribute to family income. But they are not considered productive women and also their work is underestimated as they are rural women. By educating them through financial literacy programs their standard of living can be improved."Project Financial

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"Literacy" programme is being organized by RBI to give financial literacy awareness to the public.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out the awareness of financial literacy among rural women
- To know how far the rural women are making wise judgment in saving and investment activities
- To provide suggestions that help to improve financial literacy

Methodology of the Study:

Primary data was collected from 70 respondents within Tirunelveli District. An empirical study was done based on collection of data through structured questionnaire. Convenient sampling technique was followed in selecting the samples. Statistical tools such as percentage and mean were used for data analysis.

Chi-square was used for Hypothesis test.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The questionnaire was framed based on the discussions with the people belonging to the rural areas of Tirunelveli District which includes 70 respondents. Apart from the demographic factors the questionnaire was also based on the awareness of Financial Services and Financial literacy level.

Table 1: Source of Family Income

Sl. No.	Factor	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Income from Agriculture	16	22.9
2	Income from Spouse	10	14.3
3	Income from Household work	22	31.4
4	Income from Livestock	11	15.7
5	Income from Job	11	15.7
	Total	70	100.0

Table 1 explains that the source of income of family of rural women is: Income from household work 31.4% which is the highest source of income. Income from Agriculture 22.9%, Income from live stock and Income from Job are 15.7% and income from Spouse is 14.3% respectively. It reveals that majority of the income of respondents is from household work.

Hypothesis Testing:

To know the Financial Literacy level of the Rural People based on their Education.
The Financial Literacy level of the rural people is measured on the basis of their Education.

Table 2: Educational Qualification and Financial Literacy Level

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	HL	L	N	IL	HIL	Total
1	Primary School	04	00	00	00	26	30
2	Diploma/Certificate	02	0	01	08	00	11
3	Graduate	03	0	08	00	00	11
4	Post Graduate	00	16	0	00	00	16
5	Professional	02	0	0	00	00	02
	Total	11	16	9	8	26	70

(HL-Highly Literate; L-Literate; N-Neutral; IL – Iliterate; HIL; Highly ILiterate)

Factor	value	df	Asymp.Sig(2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	181.177 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	157.909	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	35.448	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	70		

a.22 cells (88.0%) have expected less than 5. The Minimum expected count is 23. Based on the Chi-Square test, it is found that the Null Hypothesis is rejected at 5% significance level. As Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) $P < 0.05$, it is clear that the association between two variables is statistically significant.

Interpretation:

It can be stated that there is significant relationship between Education and Financial Literacy among rural women.

Table 3: Respondents' Literacy and Satisfaction level in saving in Insurance

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	Highly Agree	Agree	Moderate	Disagree	Highly Disagree	Mean Score
1	Timely help from insurance savings for sudden loss of a life	11	24	19	14	2	3.40

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	Highly Agree	Agree	Moderate	Disagree	Highly Disagree	Mean Score
2	There are different policies available in insurance to save money	11	27	14	13	5	3.37
3	Insurance gives protection to life and also property	7	14	20	13	16	2.76
4	Insurance companies are more trustable	15	24	14	13	4	3.47
5	Children's plans are more beneficial and gives good return after long time	4	31	8	15	12	3.00
6	The rural people are treated properly and respected by bank staff	6	20	11	23	10	2.84

Table 3 reveals that among all the Literacy and Satisfaction level of saving in Insurance respondents prefer "Insurance companies are more trustable" and are highly satisfied. This shows the high literacy level with mean score of 3.47 followed by the factor "Timely help from insurance savings for sudden loss of a life" with mean score of 3.40.

Table 4: Respondents' Literacy and Satisfaction level in saving in Banks

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	Highly Agree	Agree	Moderate	Disagree	Highly Disagree	Mean Score
1	Rural People are able to save their money safely in the banks	38	5	14	8	5	3.90
2	The banks are supportive to give any information about banking services	5	38	11	11	5	3.39
3	Banks have given rural people more value added services apart from loans and deposits	12	19	10	29	0	3.20
4	Banks always give preference to grant loans to people	6	22	17	13	12	2.96

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	Highly Agree	Agree	Moderate	Disagree	Highly Disagree	Mean Score
5	Credit card and debit card usage are well known by the rural people	27	13	9	11	10	3.51
6	Savings and investment Schemes are more useful to the Rural people	17	22	9	11	11	3.33
7	Rural People are treated properly and respected by Bank staff	14	20	14	16	6	3.29

Table 4 reveals that among all the Literacy and Satisfaction level of saving in Banks, the respondents prefer "Rural People are able to save their money safely in the banks" as it is being highly satisfied and shows the high literacy level with mean score of 3.90 followed by the factor "Credit card and debit card usage are well known by the rural people" with mean score of 3.51.

Table 5: Respondents' Literacy and Satisfaction level in saving in Post Office

Sl. No.	Educational Qualification	Highly Agree	Agree	Moderate	Disagree	Highly Disagree	Mean Score
1	Very convenient for saving as it is functioning in all villages	29	7	16	6	12	3.50
2	It is also more convenient for small savings	20	22	16	3	9	3.59
3	More trustable than banks and insurance	22	17	13	13	5	3.54
4	Schemes offered by post office are more attractive than banks and insurance	10	11	21	28	0	3.04
5	No loan facilities by post office	7	12	15	17	19	2.59
6	Rural postal life insurance (RPLI) is very useful for rural people	6	20	16	16	12	2.89

Table 5 reveals that among all the Literacy and Satisfaction level of savings in Post Office respondents prefer to save in post office as it is "more convenient for small savings" and is being highly satisfied and shows the high literacy level with mean score of 3.59 followed by the factor "More trustable than banks and insurance" with mean score of 3.51.

Suggestions:

- In order to increase the savings habit of the rural women, bank has to reduce the minimum balance to open account and enjoy the service of bank
- All existing financial services should be made available to the rural women in the particular region by arranging workshops such as financial literacy programs
- The banks in the rural areas should be able to communicate in their local language so that the uneducated rural women can understand the financial information of the banks
- Government can sponsor financial literacy-related courses through government agencies for the rural women and should encourage them to attend those courses

Conclusion:

All rural women need to know the services and products offered by all banks and financial institutions. The basic financial skills a women should require are saving, budgeting and maintaining simple records. They should know the importance of Financial Literacy in their personal life. Financial literacy makes people aware of the banking rules and regulations, banking schemes, Insurance and postal savings scheme etc. Without proper Financial Knowledge rural women will be facing increasing risk of making poor financial decisions which will put them in financial risks like insecure old age. Financial education plays an important role in sustainability of economic well being. Due to very low literacy level in rural areas ,rural people are not in a position to take apt financial decision in their personal life and family which simultaneously affect their financial freedom and sustainability. This research article has focused on financial literacy of rural people based on various demographic factor as well as the financial literacy level. By improving the financial literacy level of the rural women there arise better financial decision and utilization of financial services and products in proper manner that leads to social and personal development.